

Market Women's Rhymes and Calls: A Personal Folklore Analysis

In Ghana, a trip to the market is never just about shopping; it is an experience filled with vibrant sounds, persuasive voices, and rhythmic calls that make the marketplace come alive. With their melodic rhymes and playful banter, market women have a way of enticing customers, making even the most reluctant shopper buy things they never intended to buy. This verbal folklore, deeply rooted in Ghanaian culture, is not just a marketing strategy but also a reflection of tradition, community, and the artistry of persuasion. Using the four-part rubric of content, context, form, and function, this essay examines the market women's rhymes and calls as a unique form of folklore.

The content of these verbal expressions ranges from catchy sales pitches to poetic exaggerations meant to attract customers. One of my favourite market experiences is visiting Makola Market in Accra, where I am always greeted by the *asaana* seller's signature call: "*Emi ejor!*" meaning, "*It is chilling cold!*" No matter how hurried I am, I never leave without having a taste of her *asaana* (African malt), made from fermented corn and sugar, the best I have ever had. Repeated with enthusiasm, her call convinces passersby to stop and quench their thirst. Similar calls can be heard from sellers of fresh fruits, vegetables, and seafood, each crafting their own unique phrases to stand out from the crowd. Some claim, "*My tomatoes are as red as your heart!*" while others confidently declare, "*Sister, if you buy from me today, your husband will love the food!*" These witty, exaggerated, and often humorous statements are designed to engage, amuse, and, ultimately, persuade.

The context of these rhymes and calls is the bustling open-air markets of Ghana, which are pretty different from the structured supermarkets in Europe, where items are pre-packed, priced, and sold with little interaction. In Ghana, markets are lively, chaotic, and full of human connection. Unlike here, where transactions are quick and impersonal, shopping back home involves bargaining, assessing the freshness of produce, and, most importantly, engaging with sellers who take pride in their ability to charm and convince. Saturdays are peak market days, when traders and buyers fill the streets, negotiating prices and exchanging friendly banter. The social nature of these interactions turns shopping into a communal experience rather than a solitary chore.

The form of these verbal expressions is rich in rhythm, repetition, and call-and-response elements. Market women often sing or chant their sales pitches, making them both memorable and persuasive. Some sellers clap their hands to emphasise their words, while others infuse humour and proverbs to make their sales messages more engaging. The tonality and delivery of these calls are just as important as the words themselves. A fishmonger's deep, authoritative voice might reassure a customer of the quality of her goods, while a plantain seller's playful teasing can make a buyer feel special and more inclined to purchase from her.

Beyond their immediate commercial purpose, these verbal expressions serve multiple functions within Ghanaian society. First, they preserve oral traditions, as many of these rhymes and calls have been passed down through generations. They also reinforce a sense of community, as bargaining and conversation foster relationships between buyers and sellers. Some become friends and regular customers in the end. Moreover, they add an element of joy to the shopping experience, transforming the marketplace into a space of interaction, humour, and shared cultural expressions. Even in cases where a customer does not buy, the verbal exchanges remain a valued part of the experience, making shopping in Ghana's markets both social and entertaining. Cashman (2016) highlights how communicative practices shape individuals' orientation to the world, reinforcing identity and cultural belonging. The market calls I grew up with certainly shaped my understanding of culture and communication, as they were more than sales techniques but an invitation to partake in a shared heritage.

Reflecting on my own experiences, I realise that these market calls are more than just persuasive tools; they are a celebration of Ghanaian culture and identity. Every trip to Makola Market and other markets in Ghana reconnects me with this tradition, reminding me of the warmth, creativity, and resilience of the women who make the marketplace a vibrant and unforgettable space. Even now, as I navigate the quieter, structured grocery stores in Europe, I often miss the lively calls and cheerful voices that once filled my Saturday mornings. The market women's rhymes and calls remain a vital part of Ghanaian folklore, keeping cultural heritage alive in a dynamic and engaging way.

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